

On the square-free number sequence

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Abstract The main purpose of this paper is to study the number of the square-free number sequence, and give two interesting asymptotic formulas for it. At last, give another asymptotic formula and a corollary.

Keywords Square-free number sequence; Asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction

A number is called a square-free number if its digits don't contain the numbers: 0, 1, 4, 9. Let \mathcal{A} denote the set of all square-free numbers. In reference [1], Professor F. Smarandache asked us to study the properties of the square-free number sequence. About this problem, it seems that none had studied it, at least we have not seen such a paper before. In this paper, we use the elementary method to study the number of the square-free number sequence, and obtain two interesting asymptotic formulas for it. That is, let $S(x) = \sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{A}} 1$, we shall prove

the followings:

Theorem 1. For any real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\ln S(x) = \frac{\ln 6}{\ln 10} \times \ln x + O(1).$$

Theorem 2. For any real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{B}} 1 = x + O\left(x^{\frac{2 \ln 2}{\ln 10}}\right),$$

where \mathcal{B} denote the complementary set of those numbers whose all digits are square numbers.

Let \mathcal{B}' denote the set of those numbers whose all digits are square numbers. Then we have the following:

Theorem 3. For any real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{B}'} \frac{1}{n} = \ln x + \gamma - C + O\left(x^{-\frac{\ln 3}{\ln 10}}\right),$$

where C is a computable constant, γ denotes the Euler's constant.

Let \mathcal{A}' denote the complementary set of \mathcal{A} , we have following:

Corollary. For any real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{A}'} \frac{1}{n} = \ln x + \gamma - D + O\left(x^{-\frac{\ln \frac{5}{3}}{\ln 10}}\right),$$

where D is a computable constant.

§2. Proof of Theorems

In this section, we shall complete the proof of Theorems. First we need the following one simple lemma.

Lemma. For any real number $x \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{B}'} \frac{1}{n} = C + O\left(x^{-\frac{\ln \frac{5}{2}}{\ln 10}}\right).$$

Proof. In the interval $[10^{r-1}, 10^r)$, ($r \geq 2$), there are $3 \times 4^{r-1}$ numbers belong to \mathcal{B}' , and every number's reciprocal isn't greater than $\frac{1}{10^{r-1}}$; when $r = 1$, there are 4 numbers belong to \mathcal{B}' and their reciprocals aren't greater than 1. Then we have

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{B}'} \frac{1}{n} < 3 + \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} 3 \times \frac{4^r}{10^r},$$

then $\sum_{n \in \mathcal{B}'} 1$ is convergent to a constant C . So

$$\sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{B}'} \frac{1}{n} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{B}'} \frac{1}{n} - \sum_{n > x, n \in \mathcal{B}'} \frac{1}{n} = C + O\left(\sum_{r=k}^{\infty} \frac{3 \times 4^r}{10^r}\right) = C + O\left(x^{-\frac{\ln \frac{5}{2}}{\ln 10}}\right).$$

Now we come to prove Theorem 1. First for any real number $x \geq 1$, there exists a non-negative integer k , such that $10^k \leq x < 10^{k+1}$ ($k \geq 1$) therefore $k \leq \log x < k + 1$. If a number belongs to \mathcal{A} , then its digits only contain these six numbers: 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8.

So in the interval $[10^{r-1}, 10^r)$ ($r \geq 1$), there are 6^r numbers belong to \mathcal{A} . Then we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{A}} 1 \leq \sum_{r=1}^{k+1} 6^r = \frac{6}{5} \times (6^{k+1} - 1) < \frac{6^{k+2}}{5} < \frac{6^2}{5} \times x^{\frac{\ln 6}{\ln 10}},$$

and

$$\sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{A}} 1 \geq \sum_{r=1}^k 6^r = \frac{6}{5} \times (6^k - 1) \geq 6^k > \frac{1}{6} \times x^{\frac{\ln 6}{\ln 10}}.$$

So we have

$$\frac{1}{6} \times x^{\frac{\ln 6}{\ln 10}} < \sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{A}} 1 < \frac{6^2}{5} \times x^{\frac{\ln 6}{\ln 10}}.$$

Taking the logarithm computation on both sides of the above, we get

$$\ln\left(x^{\frac{\ln 6}{\ln 10}}\right) + (-\ln 6) < \sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{A}} 1 < \ln\left(x^{\frac{\ln 6}{\ln 10}}\right) + (2 \times \ln 6 - \ln 5).$$

So

$$\ln S(x) = \ln\left(\sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{A}} 1\right) = \ln\left(x^{\frac{\ln 6}{\ln 10}}\right) + O(1) = \frac{\ln 6}{\ln 10} \times \ln x + O(1).$$

This proves the Theorem 1.

Now we prove Theorem 2. It is clear that if a number doesn't belong to \mathcal{B} , then all of its digits are square numbers. So in the interval $[10^{r-1}, 10^r)$, ($r \geq 2$), there are $3 \times 4^{r-1}$ numbers don't belong to \mathcal{B} ; when $r = 1$, there are 4 numbers don't belong to \mathcal{B} . Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{B}} 1 &= \sum_{n \leq x} 1 - \sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{B}'} 1 \\ &= x + O(4 + 3 \times 4 + 3 \times 4^2 + \cdots + 3 \times 4^k) \\ &= x + O(4^{k+1}) = x + O\left(x^{\frac{2 \times \ln 2}{\ln 10}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the Theorem 2. Now we prove the Theorem 3. In reference [2], we know the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{1}{n} = \ln x + \gamma + O\left(\frac{1}{x}\right),$$

where γ is the Euler's constant.

Then from this asymptotic formula and the above Lemma, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{B}} \frac{1}{n} &= \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{1}{n} - \sum_{n \leq x, n \in \mathcal{B}'} \frac{1}{n} \\ &= \ln x + \gamma + O\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) - C + O\left(x^{-\frac{\ln \frac{5}{2}}{\ln 10}}\right) \\ &= \ln x + \gamma - C + O\left(x^{-\frac{\ln \frac{5}{2}}{\ln 10}}\right). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the Theorem 3. Now the Corollary immediately follows from the Lemma and Theorem 3.

Reference

- [1] F.Smarandache, Only problems, Not Solutions, Xiquan Publ. House, Chicago, 1993.
- [2] Tom M.Apostol, Introduction to Analytic Number Theory, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1976.